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Hunger, Poverty, Caste System and Freedom as the Major Issues in Bhabani Bhattacharya's Novel *He Who Rides a Tiger*: A Critical Study

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Abstract:

Bhabani Bhattacharya is a prominent Anglo-Indian novelist. He can be put in the category of M. R. Anand, R. K. Narayan, Raja Rao, K. A. Abbas, Arun Joshi, Anita Desai, Salman Rushdie etc. In 1967, he was given the Sahitya Akademi for his novel entitled *Shadow from Ladakh*. He focused the attention on the issues Urban-urban divide, east-west divide instead of pre- or post-independence. He discussed various issues in his novels. He accepted the art as the best means of portraying life. He never believed in the art of propaganda. Like Shakespeare, he did not paint the fairies, devils, witches, and ghosts to make the readers feel shocked. Like Mulk Raj Anand, his novels deal with the socio-economic problems of India. He is unbowed transparently vision of life. He had observed the causes and effects of hunger in Bengal Famine and he has dealt the same in '*So many Hungers*' and '*He Who Rides a Tiger*'. *He Who Rides a Tiger* is a novel of revolt and revenge as well as self-expiation. This novel focuses on the Bengal Famine, the darkest period in the history of Bengal. The people were dying of hunger. The peasants sell their lands for food, the weavers sell their looms, the artisans dispose of their tools and the fishermen sell their boats as firewood. The people of the village have become workless.

Methodology and Approach: The study of the novel '*He Who Rides a Tiger*' is partly political and mainly economic and social. The novel deals with the political situation of the country. The World War II (1939-1945) and the threat of Japanese Invasion also form part of the background that is suggested by the presence of the British soldiers in the country. The novel deals with 1943 famine that ravaged Bengal and left millions of people either dead or diseased. There is no rationing of food grains. There is no attempt at price control and checking of cornering. Boats have been destroyed as a precautionary measure. The helplessness of the people is exposed by the frantic attempt to reach Calcutta.

Outcome: *He Who Rides a Tiger* is the story of Kalo's victory of revenge against society and his learning of the principle through varied experiences, and integrity is the greatest achievements of the man. This novel shows that a man who revolts against the society cannot adjust himself and so he has to reconcile to it in the end. The whole story moves round Kalo, the hero of the novel. He is a hardworking and fortunate fellow. He performs a miracle by avenging himself on the wealthy and high-caste people. His wife has died in childbirth. He lives with his only daughter named Chandra Lekha. He goes to Calcutta in search of employment. He has to suffer on way during his journey. He has to go to jail for stealing the bananas. He has to suffer many agonies in the jail.

Keywords: **Famine, hunger, revolt, society, exploitation, The World War II, The Quit India Movement, pestilence, prostitution, freedom, caste-discrimination.**

Introduction: - Bhabani Bhattacharya is one the most famous contemporary Indian English novelists whose primary concern is to draw the attention of the society towards various problems as hunger, exploitation, caste-discrimination, pestilence, unbearable starvation. He has the power

to captivate the attention of the readers to the end of the novels. Like Jane Austan, he has written limited novels as *So Many Hungers, He Who Rides a Tiger, A Goddess named Gold, Shadow From Ladakh, Music From Mohini*. His novels abound in social and historical realities. He deals the evils of poverty, corruption, ignorance, exploitation, greed, sexual perversion, superstition etc. Like Ernest Hemingway, he was not prepared to be a part of lost generation. He is a realist and so he revealed the truth about the human nature. He never temped to write the long novels for money. Like Charles Lamb he shares his experiences with his readers. Like A. G. Gardiner he regards the readers as his friends and he never shuts his eyes towards contemporary social, political and economic problems. In an interview while conversing with Sudhakar Joshi he remarks about art and culture:

“...I hold that a novel must have a social purpose. It must place before the reader something from the society’s point of view. Art is not necessarily for art’s sake. Purposeless art and literature which is much in vogue does not appear to me a sound judgment.”

Bhabani Bhattacharya has described the theme of hunger in his novels. He has just referred the problem of hunger in the beginning of the novel *He Who Rides a Tiger*. *“His early novels, So Many Hunger and He who Rides a Tiger, which deal with the theme of hunger and concomitant theme of human degradation against the backdrop of the Bengal famine brought him high critical acclaim.”* (Abidi-17)The problem starts when Chandra Lekha comes first and wins Ashok Memorial Medal in her convent school. The students as well as their parents could not tolerate that a ‘Kamar girl’ surpasses them. The writer describes the discrimination that existed between the classes and masses in India. He becomes happy when his daughter wins the prize. But the pestilence of hunger shattered his dreams. He failed to understand what to do or what not to do. *“In the suffering of Kalo and his daughter we find a cosmic view of human*

suffering caused by a system 'corrupt with caste and cash'. Bhattacharya forcefully presents the traumatic experiences of the stark poverty of the village folk on the one hand and the 'city bugling with riches' the other hand."(Khatri-90) The writer says that Government failed to control over the black marketers. The black marketers cashed the calamity. They made money though the farmers and workers felt helpless. The artisans had to sell their tools as they failed to manage the food for themselves. Even the poor women had to compel to adopt the profession of prostitution.

Kalo goes to Calcutta in the search of employment. He leaves behind his daughter with her grandmother in the village. On the way to Calcutta, he sees many indignant people lying dead near railway line. He feels unbearable starvation and he sees the bananas on the table with owner sleeping. He thinks that the bananas owner cannot prevent him from stealing the banana. He is arrested by a policeman for stealing the bananas. He is presented before the judge. Though he speaks the truth yet he is sent to jail. The judge has never felt hunger. The novelist exposes the hollowness and prejudice of the Indian judges towards the common people and lower class people. Kalo has to suffer many agonies and the criminals were torture though they were charged with petty theft. The policemen behave them like the animals and beasts. The writer portrays the hypocrisy of the privileged class. B-10 tells kalo:

"There is one road for us-for me, for you and for all of us.....We are the scum of the earth. The boss people scorn us because they fear us. They hit us where it hurts badly in the pit of belly. We have got to hit back."(*He Who Rides a Tiger*-37)

Kalo is a kind-hearted man. He adopted a child named Obhijit. Obhijit has lost his parents. The novelist delineates Lekha's fist meeting with him in this way, *"The boy had found a half-eaten mango, rotting in its yellow skin. He was Lekha coming towards him and stiffened. He*

put the fruit back in garbage and waited, staring. His mouth opened but no voice came. He could not even whimper or beg for money.”(He Who Rides a Tiger-190) He was given the slices of bread every day. But he hides the bread slices for next day. Through the character of Obhijit, the novelist has displayed the miserable conditions of the poor children during the famine. The children like Obhijit are overlooked by the destitute people removing from the city.

Bhattacharya has dealt the problem of prostitution in the novel ‘*He Who Rides a Tiger.*’ He asks-Why are the innocent girls compelled to become harlots? Who is responsible for their poverty and hunger? After three months Kalo comes out of the prison and he finds the things worse. He has no work to do and he has nothing to eat. Compelled by hunger, he has to start to serve at a harlot house. Rajni is a prostitute and she gives the job to Kalo as an agent. But he is shocked to see his daughter there. His daughter Chandra Lekha is hit extremely hard by starvation. She has to suffer much on account of it. That is why she has to come to the brothel as we see in the end of the novel. Kalo saves his daughter from this shameful bitter life. After having rescued Chandra Lekha from brothel he wants to take the revenge on his enemies-the rich and high class people. He follows the trick of Namo Shivaya and gets success. Now Kalo wears the nine standard sacred Brahminic threads across his chest. He talks of spiritual values. He revolts against traditional social set-up. He feels free from every kind of bondage. He regards himself a Brahmin and nobody is superior to him now. He is an advocate of equality between man and man. But he recollects his past that torments him. He failed to keep himself away from the real feelings that he is a basically a ‘Kamar’. *He Who Rides a Tiger (1952)—easily Bhattacharya’s finest novel—many serious questions are posed through a, absorbing narrative of ironical reversal. ‘A a wail from the bowels of Bengal’ like, So Many Hunger, the novel tells the story of kalo, a poor blacksmith, who, jailed for stealing a bunch of banana (the magistrate’s*

question to him is, 'Why did you have to live?) vows revenge on society. He poses as a holy Brahmin, who has been vouchsafed the miraculous vision of a Shiva idol, and thrives on the fraud, until he discovers the age-old truth that he cannot dismount the tiger of his own creation without running himself; but dismount he must, in the interest of mental peace. There is an intricate cross-cross of themes here such as appearance and reality, the Haves and Haves-Nots, and religious hypocrisy." (Naik-225) Like Narayan's Raju he does not want to cheat the people. So he decides to give up the trick of Namō Shivaya (as a priest in the temple)

The novelist depicts how the rich people are savagely indifferent to the poor people. They have no sympathy with them. The rich people offer the milk to Shiva Lord in the temple for good omen. They do not think a little for the hungry people. The rich have no touch of humanity. Kalo and Vishvanath take some bath milk for the starving children, which have been offered to the temple. The rich people oppose them. They raise their voice against the rich's vision by saying that they are insulting the Ganga pouring the milk into her water while the children are lying and dying on her bank. One of the rich men says, "What absurd talk! Tens of thousands have died of hunger. What difference would a few more or a few less make? The issue at stake is bigger than those useless lives." (He Who Rides a Tiger-130) The rich are not affected by the miserable condition of the indigent people. They have not paid any attention to the cries of the hungry mass. The novelist says: "We demand the food for the hungry, 'food for all,' 'Work for all,' jail for the rice profiteers." (He Who Rides a Tiger-150)

Bhabani Bhattacharya exposes the trade of skeletons. The skeletons of these people were exported to other countries for the benefit of medical colleges. The politicians took the processions to demand food for the hungry people. Alas! The cruel policemen beat them badly. The people cried-Save us from slaughter.' But their voices were ignored by the authorities. The

military trucks were used to remove the hungry and poor people from the town and no food was distributed them to satisfy their hunger. War broke out at this time and the situation has become worse than before. The writer says:

“The dark year started three or four months from Chandra Lekha won her gold medal. It was almost the darkest in the history of Bengal. A plague took the land its grip, the plague of hunger, in the wake of war.” (He Who Rides a Tiger-15)

Bhattacharya deals with the selfishness of the people. These people practice religion for personal gain and glory. They explain the simple blind faith of uneducated people. The reason is that religion lost real glory. The people have forgotten the ethical values. Kalo establishes a temple in the name of Lord Shiva. He enjoys nice food, milk and other luxuries in this temple. Chandra Lekha is happy because there is no need to worry for the food and other things. For the people religion has become a business. B-10 tells Kalo:

“Food for soul is produced and sold like food for the stomach, and though the ways of two trades are different, you pay for both with hard cash. The temple is a market and the priest is a dealer. People are always ready to pay well for feeding the inner man.” (He Who Rides a Tiger-43)

The writer has sympathy with Have-Nots. He studied the books of Karl Marx and hence he quotes the theory of Karl Marx in his novels. Like Charles Dickens, he wrote for the sake of ethics as he likes purposeful fiction and supports the theory of art and morality. Through his novels he told the people what they were and how the situation could be changed. He wants that the poor people might fight against the tyranny of the rich people. He revealed the real picture of the contemporary society. He satirized the people who ignored the hungry miserable men, women and children. They donated wholeheartedly to the saints and the priests. But they did not

pay attention to the cries of children dying of hunger but they poured a lot of milk for bath of Lord Shiva. Kalo tells the people with confidence:

"We make gods in the image of mortals. We think of them as mortals, else who do we offer them milk? And so we must give them our best human feelings, too. We must see in Ganga a true, living mother." (He Who Rides a Tiger-143)

Kalo is the protagonist figure in the novel. He is the champion of the downtrodden and the poor people. His daughter Chandra Lekha as well as he suffers due to caste system in the society. He has capacity to befool the rich people. He feels happiness at his success plan. He overturns the age-old social order by investing himself with Brahminhood and attaining to a high social status. The caste discrimination is the worst that has been crushing Indian society for ages. Kalo tells his daughter that untouchables are helpless creatures who do not dare to go the police. He also reveals the hypocrisy of caste barriers and advocates their elimination and a sound synthesis of the different races: *"Do not dare judge me or call me a swindler. I have been as a Brahmin as any of you."* (He Who Rides a Tiger-228) Kalo and his daughter suffer gruesomely owing to hunger. Both of them lose their home, peace, profession, honesty and goodness. They decide to ride the tiger: *"Lekha sat with him on the tiger's back and they must ride on."* (He Who Rides a Tiger-143)

The novelist says that the hard working people are honest and they perform their duties very well. They do not bend before poverty and difficulty. They know how to face it. Some immoral traders come to Kalo's village to buy the young girls at high rates for harlotry in Calcutta, but the people spit on their faces. Kalo insulted them and one of these traders mutters himself:

The lowborn people would not bend but they will crack. God has sent his mighty hunger to teach the lowborn people a true lesson.”(He Who Rides a Tiger-117)

The theme of the novel signifies the title of novel, *He Who Rides a Tiger*. Riding on the tiger symbolizes man’s quest for riding on hunger. Hunger is hideous and it kills man as a tiger does. Kalo and his daughter suffer from hunger. They have lost their all on account of hunger. They decide to ride the tiger of hunger to eke out their living. The irony is in the novel that on the one hand, the indigent people are suffering from hunger and poverty; on the other hand, the rich men are busy in earning the money by hook or crook. The poor are hunger for corns, the rich for money and sex. The novel deals with the theme of hunger and utter helplessness. It shows that a man should not rebel. He should adjust.

After having come out of the jail Kalo regards B-10 as his friend. Kalo’s daughter has become an obsession for B-10. The more he tries to get rid of her, the more he feels attracted to her. Now he feels a sort of emptiness in his consciousness. But the caste difference disturbs him for some moments. In order to be equal with her he strips his sacred thread and tears it into pieces. He is impressed with Biten’s ideology. Lekha admires him. She worships him from the depth of her heart. Kalo begins to suspect with their intimacy. He remains silent about it and he trusts him. He thinks of his daughter’s marriage with Biten. He offers her hand to him and along with her half of the income of the temple. But Biten is not prepared to do so though the temple is the creation of his own plan. The blacksmith of Jharna has changed. He thinks of the future comforts of his daughter, and he tells Biten:

“Chandra Lekha has become used to a certain way of living. Losing it she will lose her happiness. Don’t you see that? (He Who Rides a Tiger-192)

In the end of the novel Lekha feels that she is also riding the tiger like her father. Now the condition has changed. She is accepted as the mother of seven fold bliss-a goddess. The people regard her as the divine woman. They seek her for blessings. But she is not happy with it and she does not want to exploit the innocent people. She becomes upset when an ordinary woman seeks her blessings for her child. After having got her blessing the woman does not survive a child and the woman bursts:

“Eater of my child, witch woman in holy clothes, calling yourself mother of bliss, may your eyes go blind. May thy womb be dead. May thy limbs be rot and drop off. May thy blood freeze. I curse thee, eater of my child.” (He Who Rides a Tiger-223) This disgusts her this time.

The novelist deals with the Indian Freedom Struggle in *He Who Rides a Tiger*. We read several references to the Indian Freedom struggles especially the ‘Quit India Movement’ of 1942. He gives a detailed description of Indians who participated in this movement and sacrificed themselves for freedom of India. It was an all-India movement and the call was made by Gandhiji against British Imperialism. The people were badly tortured in the prisons in the country during that period. The freedom fighters were called the sons of swine. The British authorities tried to suppress their voices but in vain. The Quit India Movement grew in strength everyday and even the intellectuals go the support of the masses. People from all sections of society joined the freedom struggle. Processions were taken put to draw the attention of the rulers for Home Rule. The lovers of freedom hoped for a free India in 1942-43 in spite of lathi charge and firing. There was agitation in the entire country. The novelist asserts:

“When they are fully awake and the strength surges in their limbs, they will snap the chains with a mighty effort.” (He Who Rides a Tiger-170)

Thus, like Mulk Raj Anand Bhabani Bhattacharya is a realist and he reveals the caste discrimination and exploitation in true colours in his novels. He depicts the various miseries of the people. He describes various problems of the society through the novels '*So Many Hungers and He Who Rides a Tiger*'. The famine of Bengal touches human heart. Like G. B. Shaw, he was always conscious of social purpose of his art. He portrays the tragedies of the freedom fighters. He depicts poverty, hunger, exploitation, corruption, ignorance, greedy and lustful people and the gap between the Haves and Haves-Nots. He has a positive vision of life yet he does not lose his interest in life. He hopes that love and brotherhood will prevail among the people. He hopes for a bright future of Indian people.

Works Cited:

Bhattacharya, Bhabani, *He Who Rides a Tiger*: New Delhi: Arnold Heinemann, 1977.

Khatri, C. L. in Monika Gupta's *the Novels of Bhabani Bhattacharya*: New Delhi, Atlantic Publisher and Distributors, 2002

Bhattacharya, Bhabani, *Shadow from Ladakh*: New Delhi: Hind pocket Books, 1966.

Bhattacharya, Bhabani, *So Many Hungers*: New Delhi: Arnold Heinemann, 1984.

Bhattacharya, Bhabani, *A Goddess Named Gold*: New Delhi: Arnold Heinemann, 1984

Naik, M. K., *A History of English Literature*, New Delhi; Sahitya Academy, 2014

Abidi, SHZ, *Mulk Raj Anand's Untouchable*: Bareilly: Prakash Book Depot, 1992.

Joshi, Sudhakar, An Evening With Bhabani, *The Sunday Standard*, April 27, 1969.

Bhattacharya, Bhabani, *Music for Mohini*: New Delhi: Orient Paperbacks, 1984.

Sharma, K. K., *Bhabani Bhattacharya: His Vision and Themes*; New Delhi: Abhinav Publications, 1979,